

A SPECTRAL INDEX-BASED APPROACH FOR MAPPING SALT-AFFECTED SOILS USING SENTINEL-2 IMAGERY: A CASE STUDY OF FAISALABAD, PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

SHAH NAWAZ *

Faculty of Science and Health, University of Portsmouth, United Kingdom, UK.

*Corresponding Author Email: Shahnawazuaf@hotmail.com

IQRA GHAFUOR

Institute Soil and Environmental Sciences, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan.

MUHAMMAD WASEEM RASHEED

State Key Laboratory of Urban and Regional Ecology, Research Centre for Eco-Environmental Sciences, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China.

University of Chinese Academy of Sciences (UCAS), Beijing, China.

MUHAMMAD SAFDAR

Agricultural Remote Sensing Lab, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan.

Department of Irrigation and Drainage, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan.

ABID SARWAR

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of California Merced (UCM), Merced, CA, USA.

Department of Irrigation and Drainage, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan.

SYED INTSAR HUSSAIN SHAH

Agricultural Remote Sensing Lab, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan.

Department of Irrigation and Drainage, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan.

ZAFAR IQBAL

Department of Agricultural Engineering, University of Engineering & Technology (UET), Peshawar, KPK, Pakistan.

Abstract

Salinity is a major issue in arid and semi-arid regions, affecting agricultural production and crop yield, leading to food scarcity in developing countries. However, the availability of data on salt-affected soils is hindered by resources and advanced technology. Pakistan's arid and semi-arid climate zone requires accurate management strategies due to the lack of salt-affected soil data. Advancements in GIS and remote sensing technology enable accurate monitoring of soil salinity. Thus, from June 2017 to June 2023, this study was designed to map and comprehend changes in salt-affected soils in tehsil Samundari and Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan. Sentinel-2 photos with a 10m resolution were used in this investigation. Land use land cover (LULC) maps for 2017, 2019, 2021, and 2023 were created by processing satellite pictures, calculating indices, and using supervised classification. The study's findings demonstrated that SAS's coverage area grew. There was a decrease in the amount of barren land, although it was more pronounced in Tehsil Faisalabad. However, because the land was no longer suited for agriculture and the contractors exploited it for commercial reasons, the build-up and grassland areas were expanded, increasing the build-up land. However, a rise in build-up land and salt-affected soils caused farmland to initially decline, although

an improving trend in agriculture was noted in 2023. The study's findings, however, indicated that by determining the recent extent or expansion of these problematic soils, the application of GIS and RS technology can be very helpful in the successful execution of various management and reclamation strategies. Without this information, the situation would be extremely difficult and concerning for future generations.

Keywords: Remote Sensing, GIS, Salt affected soil, LULC, Sentinel-2, NDSI, Salinity Indices.

1. INTRODUCTION

The basis of an agricultural nation's economy is its soil. Any region's ability to practice agriculture depends on the quality of the soil. Soil illness or cancer is caused by the salinity of the soil. This disease is gradually decreasing the annual yield of several fruits and crops (*Chandio et al., 2017*).

It has been demonstrated that the accuracy of salinity assessments using hyperspectral remote sensing data can be improved by identifying the individual spectral signatures of salinity affected soils (*Kumar et al., 2014; Kumar et al., 2020*).

It has been noted that the use of hyperspectral remote sensing data can improve the accuracy of salinity evaluations by identifying the distinctive spectral fingerprints of soils impacted by salt (*Kumar et al., 2014; Goldshleger et al., 2010*). Besides, according to a recent study, the salinity mapping of soils has been considerably improved using sentinel-1 SAR imaginary data with advanced machine learning algorithms (*Hoa et al., 2019*).

Apart from hyperspectral data, multispectral satellite video imaging has also contributed to production of maps of soils that have been degraded by salts. Some of the investigations carried out have employed the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) normally used to detect vegetative covers in determining the salt levels in bare soils and vegetated soils (*Gojiya et al. 2023; Allbed & Kumar, 2013*).

Salinized soils have a spectral signature that facilitate separation of salty areas from normal territories, particularly, in the visible and near-infrared bands (*Gautam et al., 2011; Gorji et al., 2019*). In addition, the temporal aspect of satellite imaging allows seasonal changes of soil salinization to be assessed, providing a more dynamic view of salinization (*Chen et al., 2019; Ma et al., 2020*).

There are several advantages of assessing soil salinity using satellite based remote sensing. These technologies can be said to give a rapid, simple and holistic approach in collection of both quantitative and qualitative geographical information (*Gojiya et al. 2023; Gorji et al., 2019*).

They enable one to carry out wide scale assessments that would be impractical using traditional on-site approaches, which tend to be labour intensive and at times very limited (*Cui et al., 2022; Hui & Liu, 2013*). It is therefore argued that this approach provides a better way of incorporating information from satellite images and understanding the dynamics of salt-affected soils.

For the past thirty years, many research works have been done on the mapping and monitoring of salt affected soils using satellite images and multispectral sensors such as Landsat Thematic Mapper, Landsat Multispectral Scanner System, ETM+, SPOT, Terra-ASTER, LISS-III and IKONOS (*Dwivedi, 2001; Verma et al., 1994*).

In the USA, the authors used Landsat TM and decision tree analysis (DTA) to zone Malheur County in the hydrogeological mapping of soil salinity, the results exhibit reasonable divisions of EC values to the reflectance bands of Landsat and showed a more blanket effect of salinized soil. Many researchers have proved effectiveness of Landsat ETM+ data in the mapping of soil salinity with accurate results of 83.6% in Thailand.

Mapping of soil salinity with the use of Landsat-7 ETM+ and ancillary data and data introduced need several recent progresses are the use of Terra ASTER images for mapping soils with chlorides and sodium sulphate content, and the use of OLI imagery in which multivariate statistical analyses and field data prediction of soil salt in Egypt has been explored. (*Mehrijardi et al., 2008; Yu et al., 2010; Kleidman et al., 2005; Huang et al., 2005; El-Hamid et al., 2023*).

Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information System (GIS) are recent technology applied to obtain information concerning the surface of the planet. RS involves using sensors to detect and record energy, followed by processing and analysing the data using image processing techniques. In most remote sensing, the interaction between radiation and the target is involved.

Different Earth features absorb and reflect different portions of the electromagnetic spectrum, providing information about salinity and sodicity (*Allbed and Kumar, 2013*). Thematic Mapper, a satellite that provides observations in visible to thermal bands, primarily supplies images from Landsat and Sentinel-2 satellites, transmitting data back to the planet's observation and processing unit (*Abdullaev et al., 2023*).

It is limited to arid or semi-arid regions (*Ahmad et al., 2002*) salinization of the soil is a major environmental problem in arid and semi-arid regions of the world, including Pakistan (*Wang et al., 2023*). Most of these soils are found in Sindh and Punjab, but they are found in several Pakistani provinces, including Rakh Dera Chal (Lahore), Shorkot, and Lodhran. (*Rao et al., 2023*), consequently causing food insecurity (*Ahmed et al., 2022*). The area of SAS is growing in district Faisalabad, Pakistan, specifically Pakka Anna (*Ashraf et al., 2007*).

Sustainable agriculture necessitates an accurate assessment of SAS as well as the identification of suitable cultivable land. (*Naz et al., 2022*). Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) have become more important for mapping and monitoring salt-affected soils (SAS). (*Ait Haddou et al., 2023; Matinfar et al., 2023*). Accordingly, the purpose of this research is to assess and map the salt-affected soils using remote sensing techniques in tehsil Samundari and Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Absence of moisture within soil and triumphant sod alkaline also known as sodicity remain among the most dangerous stress factors for plants growing in dry and semidry territories particularly in Pakistan. Salinity, as well as sodicity, induced infertility expansion encroached over 5,727 ha of land (*Jan et al., 2023*). Conditions of climate change along with the different characteristics of soils and human activities are the many factors that induce soil salinization (*Farooqi et al., 2023; Safdar et al. 2024*).

Poverty posing environmental structures including health and biological productivity is greatly underestimated in the SAS regions of Pakistan which have little information on the shifts with time. (*Kabiraj et al., 2023; Mohamed et al., 2023*). Soil salinization is one of the essential problems for the sustainable environment as well as agricultural yield especially for the semi-arid & arid areas.

It can be detrimental to the ecosystems, reduce the effectiveness of agriculture and eventually cause soil to become useless. Effective mapping regarding salt affected soils helps in formulating intervention and restoration requirements for effective land use. The use of the recent advancement of remote sensing particularly satellite photos has changed the traditional way of examining the salinity of the soil. This research investigates a spectral index-based approach for mapping salt-affected soils using satellite data, offering valuable insights into the geographical distribution of soil salinity. This approach could lead to more sustainable agricultural production and better land management strategies.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study area

Punjab, a crucial province in Pakistan, is known for its agricultural production. The study area includes Samundari and Faisalabad, two tehsils in Faisalabad district, also known as Manchester due to its past record of cotton production. Table 1 and Fig. 1 provide important information. The geographical coordinates for Samundari range from 31° 35' 2" to 31° 3' N and 72° 57' to 72° 57' E. In comparison, Faisalabad is located between 31° 02' to 31° 45' N and 72° 50' to 73° 22' E. Both Samundari and Faisalabad are in the arid climatic zone, with summers being hot and extremely hot.

Samundari has maximum temperatures of 56.15 °C, while Faisalabad has 49 °C. June is the warmest month, with Samundari averaging 45.69 °C and Faisalabad at 33.9 °C. Winter temperatures vary between the regions. Samundari experiences a maximum daytime temperature of 23.27°C, while Faisalabad experiences a daytime temperature of 27°C, with nighttime temperatures dropping to 0°C.

January is the coldest month, with Faisalabad's average temperature of 12.5°C. Samundari experiences 49.28 mm of rainfall annually, while Faisalabad receives 526 mm. The highest relative humidity is 46.68% in February, while it drops to 19.14% in May. In contrast, Faisalabad experiences 66.02% in January and 28.89% in May.

Table 1: Features of the study areas

STUDY AREA	SAMUNDARI	FAISALABAD
GEO-COORDINATES	31° 35' to 31° 3' N and 72° 57' to 72° 57' E	31° 02' to 31° 45' N and 72° 50' to 73° 22' E
CLIMATIC ZONE	Arid	Arid and Semiarid
SUMMER	Long and hot Max temp rising to 56.15 °C	Long and hot Max temp rising to 49 °C
WARMEST MONTH	June (45.69 °C)	June (average temp 33.9 °C)
WINTER	Max temp 23.27 °C (day) Min approximately	Max temp 27 °C (day) Min approximately 0 °C (night)
COLDEST MONTH	January (average temp	January (average temp 12.5 °C)
TOTAL ANNUAL RAINFALL	49.28 mm	526 mm
HIGHEST RELATIVE HUMIDITY	Feb (46.68%)	January (66.02 %)
LOWEST RELATIVE HUMIDITY	May (19.14)	May (28.89%)

Figure 1: Geographical Location map of the Study area

2.2 Data Used

This study makes use of USGS Sentinel-2 satellite data (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>) for the years 2017–2023, which records cloud-free sceneries. Soil salts are detected by Landsat spectral data; nevertheless, successful analysis requires digital image analysis and visual interpretation (Davis et al., 2019). Identifying salt-affected soils on False Colour Composite (FCC) or black-and-white prints is the visual interpretation process. ERDAS and ArcGIS Pro are used for digital image analysis, and SAS's spectral reflectance is an

important factor (Srinivasan et al., 2022). The study offers insightful information on soil salts. (Fig. 2).

Table 2: Sentinel 2 satellite band information

Band Name	Central Wavelength (μm)	Resolution (m)
Band 1 Coastal aerosol	0.443	60
Band 2 Blue	0.49	10
Band 3 Green	0.56	10
Band 4 Red	0.665	10
Band 5 Red Edge - 1	0.705	20
Band 6 Red Edge - 2	0.74	20
Band 7 Red Edge - 3	0.783	20
Band 8 NIR	0.842	10
Band 8A Red Edge - 4	0.865	20
Band 9 Water vapor	0.945	60
Band 10 Cirrus	1.375	60
Band 11 SWIR-1	1.61	20
Band 12 SWIR-2	2.19	20

Figure 2: Overall Methodology Flowchart

2.3. Principal Component Analysis & Implementation

Principal component analysis (PCA) is a widely used technique for feature extraction as well as data reduction in remote sensing and image processing. It can also be used to identify soil salinity using Sentinel-2 data along with other multispectral satellite photography. The original data is transformed into a new set of non-correlated variables called principal components (PCs) using PCA, where the top few PCs preserve most of the variance in the original data and can be used for further analysis like categorization and visualization (Dwivedi, 2007).

2.4 Supervised Image Classification

Supervised image classification is a method used to classify images based on user-defined signatures. Sentinel-2 satellite images are used for tracking soil salinity due to their high resolution, multispectral capabilities, and frequent return durations. The training data for this method is collected and annotated to represent various saline levels. In this study, a maximum likelihood supervised algorithm for SAS detection was implemented, assigning each pixel in the satellite picture to the class most likely to provide the pixel's observed spectral signature. The satellite images were pre-processed using atmospheric and radiometric correction, band combination, layer stacking, and image enhancements to remove distortions and improve image quality. The resulting images were used to extract the region of interest, Salalah City, for the classification of LULC. The supervised maximum likelihood classification (MLC) algorithm determines the probability of each pixel being associated with a specific LULC class as applied by (Sharma and Mondal, 2006; Tuia et al., 2009; Elnaggar and Noller, 2010; Taghadosi et al., 2019; Sadiq et al., 2020; Moisa & Gameda, 2021; Alsharif et al., 2022; Gupta & Singh, 2022). Richards' 1991 MLC algorithm used discriminant functions to compute and interpret satellite pixel spectral signatures for different LULC classes, determining the probability of each pixel belonging to a specific class. This method allowed for the calculation of spectral signatures.

$$g_i [x] = \ln * p[w_i] - \frac{1}{2} \ln |\Sigma_i| - \frac{1}{2} [x - x_i]^T \Sigma_i^{-1} [x - m_i], \quad (1)$$

In this equation, "i" represents the Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) class, "x" represents the number of bands in the satellite image, "p[w_i]" is the probability of class "w_i" in the classified image, "|\Sigma_i|" is the covariance matrix factor related to the data of class "w_i", "\Sigma_i⁻¹" is the inverse matrix, and "m_i" represents the mean vector. The equation determines the likelihood of each pixel belonging to a specific LULC class by comparing its spectral signature with known LULC classes. The pixels are divided into six categories: Bare land, built-up areas, Cropland, water bodies, salt-affected soil, and Grassland. Bare ground lands are exposed soils without vegetation, built-up areas are residential, commercial, and industrial developments, Cropland is agricultural and natural vegetation, water bodies are streams, rivers, lakes, and reservoirs, and salt-affected soils are water-stressed soils.

2.5 Soil Salinity Indices (SSI)

This study used five soil salinity indices (SSI) to accurately detect soil salinity. SSIs rely on the spectral responses of salty soils in different bands. As soil surface salinity

increases, the spectral response changes. The presence of salts in soil results in a difference between the VIS and NIR bands and the NIR and MIR bands, making it crucial to consider these bands to differentiate between saline and non-saline soils. ArcGIS Pro was used to create thematic maps using raster and vector GIS datasets. The distribution of saline soils in the study area was quantified using area calculations (*Schmid et al., 2008; Narmada et al., 2015*).

Table 3: Formulae / Description for different Indices

Indices	Formulae / Description	References
Normalized difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	$(\text{NIR}-\text{RED})/(\text{NIR}+\text{RED})$	Khan et al.,2005
Normalized difference salinity index (NDSI)	$(\text{Green}-\text{SWIR}) / (\text{Green}+\text{SWIR})$	Khan et al.,2005
Bare Soil Index (BSI)	$((\text{Red}+\text{SWIR}) - (\text{NIR}+\text{Blue})) / ((\text{Red}+\text{SWIR}) + (\text{NIR}+\text{Blue}))$	Diek et al., 2017
Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI)	$2.5 * (\text{B8} - \text{B4}) / (\text{B8} + 6 * \text{B4} - 7.5 * \text{B2} + 1)$	Liu et al., 2003
Ratio Vegetation Index (RVI)	NIR / Red	Anderson, 1993

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Selecting Optimal Bands and Principal Component Analysis:

The selection of bands from satellite images is crucial for detecting desired features, as images contain redundant information that must be suppressed. Initial screening on the raw image is done to select optimal bands, and PCA is applied to rectified images to avoid redundant information. This spectral reduction method removes redundancy without losing vital information.

Four initial components comprised more than 90% of the information, selected using correlation and covariance statistics. Table 4 (a, b, and c) shows the covariance, correlation, and eigenvalues of the PCA analysis on Sentinel 2 data for 2019. (*Dwivedi, 1996; Yang et al., 2012; Rahmati and Hamzehpour, 2018; Abd El-Hamid et al., 2023*). The study selected principal components based on eigenvalue percentage, revealing that most information is redundant due to the presence of broad bands. 89% of the information was contained in PC 1, but three more PCs were taken to highlight salt-affected soil.

Different classification algorithms were used to identify LULC over the study area. The general LULC for semi-arid areas like Faisalabad and Samundari tehsils is dominant with built-up, agriculture, grassland, and rangeland. Figure 3 generate an image with three PCs (principal components), showing more spectral variability. Blue and light blue tone depicts urban class spread across the city. It is to be noted that the feature space of each PC was studied in Erdas Imagine which provided very useful information to classify areas into various classes.

Table 4a: Table showing Covariance Matrix

PC	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	95549	99791	114070	113838	133152	148620	136618	156770	158122	127948
2	99791	105014	121524	120355	138109	153356	141130	161641	166955	136649
3	114070	121524	149198	141945	144166	154697	141872	162341	194240	169121
4	113838	120355	141945	141954	156447	171837	158219	181127	197015	164514
5	133152	138109	144166	156447	225867	264515	244166	281648	229247	163840
6	148620	153356	154697	171837	264515	314624	290330	335568	255748	174715
7	136618	141130	141872	158219	244166	290330	271279	310024	236285	161041
8	156770	161641	162341	181127	281648	335568	310024	358731	271388	183934
9	158122	166955	194240	197015	229247	255748	236285	271388	283798	230274

Table 4b: Table showing Correlation Matrix

PC	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	1.00	1.00	0.96	0.98	0.91	0.86	0.85	0.85	0.96	0.92
2	1.00	1.00	0.97	0.99	0.90	0.84	0.84	0.83	0.97	0.94
3	0.96	0.97	1.00	0.98	0.79	0.71	0.71	0.70	0.94	0.97
4	0.98	0.99	0.98	1.00	0.87	0.81	0.81	0.80	0.98	0.97
5	0.91	0.90	0.79	0.87	1.00	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.91	0.76
6	0.86	0.84	0.71	0.81	0.99	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.86	0.69
7	0.85	0.84	0.71	0.81	0.99	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.85	0.69
8	0.85	0.83	0.70	0.80	0.99	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.85	0.68
9	0.96	0.97	0.94	0.98	0.91	0.86	0.85	0.85	1.00	0.96
10	0.92	0.94	0.97	0.97	0.76	0.69	0.69	0.68	0.96	1.00

Table 4c: Table showing Eigenvalues

PC	Eigen Value	Percent	Accumulative %
1	1921643	89.41	89.41
2	207998	9.68	99.09
3	12295	0.57	99.66
4	2396	0.11	99.77
5	1753	0.08	99.85
6	1443	0.07	99.92
7	970	0.05	99.97
8	384	0.02	99.98
9	212	0.01	99.99
10	121	0.01	100.00

Figure 3: Map showing PCA for 2017, 2019, 2021, and 2023 Years

3.2. Spectral Profiles Results for Soil Salinity

The spectral profile is a graph of the reflectance or radiance values of various light wavelengths recorded by remote sensing sensors. Researchers like Gorji et al. (2019) have used specialized sensors to analyse the spectral characteristics of soil samples from regions with different salt levels. It has been found that the reflection of light varies with the level of salinity, with low-salinity soils reflecting more light at specific wavelengths, especially in the visible and near-infrared spectrum. As salinity rises, reflectance patterns may alter, with higher reflectivity in the shortwave infrared area and lower reflectance in the visible and near-infrared. High salt soils exhibit higher reflectivity in the shortwave infrared area and lower reflectance in the visible and near-infrared, possibly due to salts that absorb more light in the visible spectrum but are more reflective in the shortwave infrared range as shown in Figure 4. (Gorji et al. 2019).

Figure 4: Spectral response of salt-affected soils of three different locations

3.3. Satellite Image Visual Interpretation:

Visual interpretation of satellite images is a process that involves examining and understanding the data provided by satellites. It helps in identifying land use, natural features, and built-up areas using tone, band combinations, pattern detection, and ground information. In Samundari and Faisalabad, this study identified five major classes of Saline Areas (SAs): Built-up Areas, Vegetation (cropland and grassland), Soil or Bare Land, Saline Area, and Water Bodies. The FCC index is crucial for understanding variations on land surface. Images of Sentinel 2 for 2017, 2019, 2021, and 2023 were divided into different colours based on land cover. The cyan-light blueish tone indicates urban areas, while the saline area is harder to interpret using visual image techniques. The water body is shown in blue to dark blue and black colour shades, while bright red indicates agriculture or healthy vegetation. The reddish tone shows vegetative areas, which decreased significantly in 2023 compared to 2017. Discriminating visually between bare-land, sparse built-up, saline, and sand areas is not easy and generally not very

effective. Saline areas show an increasing trend in soil salinity due to various factors, including agricultural practices and irrigation practices as shown in Figure 5 respectively (Mohammed et al. 2021; Ji et al. 2022).

Figure 5: Sentinel-2 satellite image showing FCC for 2017, 2019, 2021, and 2023

3.4 Salinity and Land Use Land Cover (LULC) Class Interpretation:

Sustainable land management and farming require a deep understanding of the relationship between land use and soil salinity. By implementing effective land use planning, irrigation methods, and water management strategies, soil salinity can be reduced while preserving soil health and productivity. Monitoring LULC and soil salinity variations over time can help identify potential issues and implement mitigation measures as shown in Figures 6, 7, 8 and 9 respectively.

Human activities and environmental conditions significantly influence soil salinity levels. In our study area, salt-affected soil (SAS) increased due to salt accumulation, which can be caused by excessive salt concentrations in irrigation water or poor drainage. This can lead to soil salinity levels rising over time, impacting crop production and growth. Urbanization, which often results in altered drainage patterns, less vegetation, and increased impervious surfaces, can also contribute to soil salinity by causing saltwater intrusion into freshwater aquifers (Mohammed et al. 2021; Ji et al. 2022; Raza et al. 2024).

The Temporal LULC classification results show prominent classes such as barren land, built-up, crops, grassland, salt-affected soils, and water. The salt-affected area in Faisalabad has increased from 7% to 18.8% from 2017 to 2023, while in Samundari Tehsil, it remains at 10.6%. The statistical distribution and comparison of LULC in both areas show no significant change, with a value of 10.6% in both cases. The results are supported by research by (), which supports the findings.

The analysis of LULC statistics for 2017-2023 in both tehsils of Faisalabad district reveals significant trends. In 2017, the salt-affected area was only 7%, increasing to 8.6% in 2019 and 11.9% in 2023. In 2021, it jumped to 14%, possibly due to high industrial, agricultural, and anthropogenic activities. The barren land in Tehsil Faisalabad decreased from 40% to 33%. In Tehsil Samundari, barren land decreased from 35% to 29%, similar to tehsil Faisalabad as shown in Figure 10.

Table 5: LULC Area Calculation for Faisalabad Tehsil

LULC Class	2017 Area Sq. km.	2017 %	2019 Area Sq. km.	2019 %	2021 Area Sq. km.	2021 %	2023 Area Sq. km.	2023 %
Cropland	239.65	15	271.60	17	241.84	15.1	288.18	18.1
Barren Land	639.06	40	509.16	31.9	457.93	28.6	530.41	33.2
Built-Up	319.53	20	285.48	17.9	318.84	19.9	364.27	22.8
Grassland	255.62	16	378.61	23.70	340.27	21.3	194.91	12.2
Salt affected Soil	111.83	7	137.59	8.6	226.85	14.2	300.36	18.8
Water	31.95	2	14.37	0.9	14.37	0.9	14.37	0.9
Total Area	1597.67		1597.67		1597.67		1597.67	

Table 6: LULC Area Calculation for Samundari Tehsil

LULC Class	2017 Area Sq. km.	2017 %	2019 Area Sq. km	2019 %	2021 Area Sq. km.	2021 %	2023 Area Sq. km.	2023 %
Cropland	270.50	28.2	267.52	27.9	237.10	24.7	293.240	30.6
Barren Land	270.50	34.8	233.06	24.3	256.80	26.7	279.94	29.1
Built-Up	72.15	7.6	97.312	10.2	63.55	6.6	93.51	9.7
Grassland	179.70	18.7	272.22	28.4	226.94	23.6	171.83	17.9
Salt affected Soil	101.75	10.6	80.63	8.4	169.13	17.7	101.75	10.6
Water	0.959	0.1	7.679	0.8	6.719	0.7	21.118	2.2
Total Area	959.93		959.93		959.97		959.93	

Figure 6: Land use land cover map of 2017 and % Graph

Figure 7: Land use land cover map of 2019 and % Graph

Figure 8: Land use land cover map of 2021 and % Graph

Figure 9: Land use land cover map of 2023 and % Graph

Figure 10: Showing temporal trends of Land use Land cover

3.5 Image Indices & Interpretation

3.5.1. Bare Soil Index (BSI)

Remote sensing and satellite imaging often use the BSI to detect bare soil or exposed ground surfaces. The BSI ranges from -1 to 1, with negative values indicating thick vegetation, near-zero values indicating mixed pixels, and positive values indicating uncovered ground or bare soil.

The likelihood of a pixel reflecting bare soil or non-vegetated surfaces increases with increasing BSI values. In Figure 11, greenish shade indicates vegetation cover, while off-white to light brown tonal variation shows bare soil and darker brown tones represent dense built-up. Values close to zero indicate bare soil or salinity as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Showing BSI for 2017, 2019, 2021, and 2023

3.5.2. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

NDVI values range from -1 to 1, with negative numbers indicating no vegetation or bodies of water, and close to 0 representing voids, rock surfaces, or clouds. Higher numbers indicate denser vegetation, while positive values indicate vegetation presence and health. Lower NDVI values in specific areas may indicate salt levels, but other factors like cloud cover, meteorological conditions, and vegetation type can also influence these values, making NDVI insufficient for accurately quantifying soil salinity as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Showing NDVI for 2017, 2019, 2021, and 2023

3.5.3. Ratio Vegetation Index (RVI) or Simple Ratio

Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) and NDVI are more popular indices that are used more frequently, however, RVI is still a useful tool in some circumstances. The results of this study are shown in Figure 13. Regarding soil salinity, RVI may also be indirectly correlated with soil salt levels. Vegetation may exhibit signs of stress or slower growth in regions where soil salinity is a problem. As a result, the NIR reflectance (numerator) and red reflectance (denominator) in the RVI formula may both decline. As a result, saline-affected areas may have lower RVI values than non-affected places. It's crucial to remember that, like NDVI, RVI does not directly measure soil salinity as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Showing RVI for 2017, and 2023

3.5.4. Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI)

The reflectance values in the red, blue, and near-infrared (NIR) bands of the satellite image were used to calculate the EVI. Typically, the Enhanced Vegetation Index values fall between -1 and 1, with higher positive values signifying healthier, denser vegetation and lower positive values signifying sparse or stressed vegetation. If we interpret our

results as shown in EVI Figures 14 for the years 2017 and 2023 we can see clear differences in their values, the index is not suitable for salinity mapping but depicts a clear indication of saline or bare soil areas in brown and yellow tones. It is pertinent to mention that it also mixes bare land and built-up areas as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Showing EVI for 2017, and 2023

3.5.5. Normalized Difference Salinity Index

The Normalized Difference Salinity Index (NDSI) is a spectral indicator used in remote sensing to measure soil salinity in agricultural and natural settings. It uses reflectance coefficients of two light wavelengths, visible and shortwave infrared, to track and map salt and salt-affected soils. The NDSI values range from -1 to 1, with negative values representing low salinity and positive values indicating higher salinity levels. The magnitude of the NDSI value estimates the soil salinity level, with higher absolute values indicating more significant salinity. These maps are crucial for farmers, land managers, and researchers to pinpoint locations with different salt levels and use proper soil management techniques and irrigation systems to reduce the impact of salinity on crop yields and agricultural production. They can also help track long-term changes in salt-

affected soils, enabling pre-emptive actions to combat soil degradation and sustainably manage agricultural land. The index must be read in conjunction with other indices to ensure accurate results as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Showing NDSI for 2017, 2019, 2021, and 2023

3.6 Discussions

Saline soils (SAS) are a significant threat to agriculture, primarily found in arid and semiarid regions, covering 7% of the Earth's total land area. The United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization estimates that saline soil covers 397 million hectares of the world's land. Factors contributing to SAS generation in Pakistan include parent material, high temperature, low rainfall, arid and semiarid climatic conditions, and poor management practices. Pakistan, an agricultural country with a total area of 79.7 Mha, has 80% of its land in arid and semi-arid areas, which are directly linked to SAS generation. Out of 20.36 Mha of total cultivated land, approximately 6.3 Mha is salt affected. However, a significant part of the SAS (3.5 Mha) is cultivated for rice, wheat, cotton, and sugarcane, but production is low. Estimates suggest that the yields of these crops on moderately salt-affected soils are 64, 62, 59, and 68%, respectively. Remote sensing images are utilized for digital mapping of soil salinization at various scales, with white salt crusts, halophytic plants, and salt-tolerant crops playing a crucial role in detecting salt-affected soil (SAS) from remotely sensed data. (Ashraf et al., 2007; Liu et al. 2019; Matinfar et al. 2023;).

This study analyses remotely sensed data to understand changes in the land use and land cover (LULC) of tehsil Samundari and Faisalabad using image analysis software, primarily in ArcGIS Pro software. RS technologies were used due to their vast application, capability, and cost-effectiveness. The study aims to understand the change in area covered by SAS in these areas. Various indices, such as NDVI, NDSI, NDBI, MNDWI, BSI, EVI, RVI, and PCA, were identified as important predictor variables for SAS prediction. Vegetation is a crucial factor affecting the accuracy of SAS monitoring estimation, but there are no universal vegetation indices that can achieve satisfactory results under any environmental conditions. Vegetation indices are more responsive to changes in soil salinity under dense vegetation. After analysing these indices, LULC maps and area graphs were generated to understand temporal variations. The study aims to provide a more accurate understanding of SAS monitoring in these areas. (Metternicht and Zinck, 2003; Zhang et al., 2011; Yang et al., 2012; Allbed et al., 2014; Gorji et al., 2019; He et al. 2023).

The study uses NDVI to identify salt-affected soil (SAS) in Samundari and Faisalabad based on plant growth and condition. Stress conditions, such as dehydration, damage cell structure and affect chlorophyll formation. Plants show reduced chlorophyll content and increased water stress, supported by field research. SAS can be explained by cropping patterns like cotton, rice, alfalfa, spiny sesbania, and Trifolium Alexandrinum. Cotton or paddy, cultivated on irrigated land, is an ideal indirect indicator for soil salinity, making it a useful indicator in various studies. The presence of SAS can also be explained by cropping patterns in these areas, such as cotton, rice, alfalfa, spiny sesbania, and Trifolium Alexandrinum. (Metternicht and Zinck, 2008; Allbed et al., 2014; He et al. 2023; Kaplan et al. 2023; Ali et al. 2024). Cotton production in Faisalabad has significantly decreased due to poor irrigation water and white fly attacks. Maize has gained importance

as an economic crop. Soil salinity affects crop performance on saline soils like paddy, wheat, barley, and cotton, assessed the severity and extent of soil salinity's economic impact on crop production and distinguished saline soils from non-affected ones based on high correlations between NDVI values and EC.

The study used vegetation indices RVI and NDVI to measure soil salinity in agricultural and natural settings. The NDSI index showed an increase in soil salinity from 2017 to 2023 in both districts. The higher values of NDSI indicated the presence of stressed crops in various parts of the district. NDSI is more successful in extracting different classes of salinity. A crusted saline soil surface is generally smoother than a non-saline surface and exhibits high reflectance in visible and NIR bands. LCLU maps were prepared, and it was observed that built up, water bodies, and cropland did not significantly vary during this period. However, grassland, bare land, and salt-affected soils showed variability. Climate pattern shift is one of the most important reasons for this variability. The graph shows the temporal change of LULC over the study period from 2017 to 2023. (Rao *et al.*, 1996; Khan *et al.*, 2005; Ashraf *et al.*, 2007; He *et al.* 2023; Raza *et al.* 2024).

The graphs showed that salt-affected soils increased from 2017 to 2021, while bare land decreased in both tehsils, with Faisalabad having a higher percentage. However, bare land increased in 2023, while build-up and grass land increased from 2017 to 2021. This increase in bare land is linked to salt-affected soils and commercialization, driven by factors such as population growth, economic development, and environmental changes. In Samundari tehsil, commercialization has increased over the past few years, while in Faisalabad, grassland has increased due to government-initiated agricultural companies. Crop land trends showed significant differences between Faisalabad and Samundari, with Faisalabad experiencing less increase in crop land due to urbanization and commercialization. Samundari increasing trend in adaptation of agricultural initiatives, such as sowing winter and summer maize and applying amendments, may decrease bare land and increase crop land. Monitoring these trends is crucial for sustainable development and land management (He *et al.* 2023; Kaplan *et al.* 2023; Hadeed *et al.* 2024).

The area covered by salt-affected soils (SAS) in both tehsils is increasing, but this trend is not as significant in Samundari compared to Faisalabad. This increase may be due to increased interest in new crops and amendments, but it is alarming that salt-affected soils are increasing. The increase in SAS is linked to various factors, including natural factors like climate and soil composition, and anthropogenic factors like poor quality irrigation water. Climate data from 2015 to 2021 shows that increased temperature and decreased precipitation significantly contribute to the increase in SAS. Most crops are harvested and sown before June, so June provides more data directly from land. However, farmers in the region are gaining timely information from government initiatives and adopting proactive approaches to improve crop productivity. Changes in groundwater levels in the region, often due to rain, irrigation canal water, and wastewater seepage, also affect

agriculture and open doors to industrialization, particularly in Faisalabad Tehsil, the industrial hub of Punjab. (Ashraf et al., 2007; Kaplan et al. 2023; Raza et al. 2024).

The mapping of salt-affected soils in Samundari, a region not highly populated and industrial, was challenging due to its lack of a highly populated area. Various methods were used to identify salt-affected soils, including classification and the use of indices like NDVI, NDSI, GDVI, EVI, and BSI. The study found a high saline region, identified by salts accumulating on the surface. However, some regions have high salinity or salt-affected soils due to poor management of canal irrigation water and groundwater table. The salinity in this region is also due to the application of fertilizers on crops, which are then converted into salts by rain or flood irrigation. To overcome the issue of multiple indices like NDSI and NDVI, NDBI and BSI were preferred to distinguish salt-affected bare soil and built-up. These indices have been used in many studies, with BSI and NDSI, along with PCA, showing promising results in identifying salt-affected soils. The overall percentage of salt-affected soils in the study area from 2017, 2019, 2021 and 2023 was about 8%, 9%, 15%, and 11%, respectively. The trend showed an increasing percentage of salt-affected areas (Khan et al., 2005; Matsushita et al. 2007; Liu et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2013; Wu, 2014; Elhag, 2016; Kaplan et al. 2023)

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Soil salinity is a global issue that requires accurate mapping and monitoring for agricultural planning and food security. Traditional field-based methods were qualitative and subjective, while satellite data offered a more efficient approach. This study used GIS and remote sensing methods to measure and map soil salinity in tehsil Samundari and Faisalabad, generating accurate maps that highlighted notable spatial salinity differences. Remote sensing was a promising tool for mapping salt-affected soils, and this study demonstrated its potential in addressing this global problem. Traditional field-based methods were often time-intensive, qualitative, and limited in spatial reach. Remote sensing and GIS technologies enabled broader spatial coverage, frequent updates, and higher accuracy, as demonstrated in the salinity mapping of tehsil Samundari and Faisalabad. This work supported the value of geospatial techniques in providing essential insights for improved land management, agricultural practices, and environmental conservation.

The integration of remote sensing-based salinity data into agricultural planning is crucial for addressing long-term productivity and land health. Regular assessments using advanced remote sensing techniques can support timely interventions and prevent land degradation. Sustainable land management practices, such as crop rotation and salinity-tolerant crops, can mitigate the adverse effects of salinity. Further research and investment in advanced sensors and digital image analysis techniques can enhance soil salinity mapping precision and efficiency. Training local agricultural and environmental agencies in GIS and remote sensing applications can improve their capacity to effectively address environmental challenges.

Funding

No Funding

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Availability of data and material

All data included in this study are available upon request by contacting the corresponding author.

References

- 1) Abd El-Hamid, H. T., Alshehri, F., El-Zeiny, A. M., & Nour-Eldin, H. (2023). Remote sensing and statistical analyses for exploration and prediction of soil salinity in a vulnerable area to seawater intrusion. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 187, 114555.
- 2) Abdullaev I., Bekchanov M., and M. Ergashev, "Monitoring soil salinity using Landsat and Sentinel-2 satellites," *Journal of Arid Environments* 207, 104514 (2023).
- 3) Ahmad N., M. Qadir, and S. Ahmed "Agricultural production of saline-alkali soils in Pakistan: Influences and management," *Land Degradation & Development* 13(1), 49-62 (2002).
- 4) Ahmed R., S. Ali, and A. Hussain "Food security challenges due to soil salinity in Pakistan," *Journal of Food Security* 10(1), 23-28 (2022).
- 5) Ait Haddou R., Lamouroux C., and Z. Belala "Use of remote sensing and GIS for monitoring soil salinity in arid and semi-arid regions," *Remote Sensing* 15(2), 345 (2023).
- 6) Ali, K., Nishtar, Z., Sabir, R. M., & Safdar, M. (2024). Biosensors for Environmental Monitoring in the Smart Agriculture Sector. In A. Khang (Ed.), *Agriculture and Aquaculture Applications of Biosensors and Bioelectronics* (pp. 138-157). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-2069-3.ch007>
- 7) Allbed, A. and Kumar, L. (2013). Soil salinity mapping and monitoring in arid and semi-arid regions using remote sensing technology: a review. *Advances in Remote Sensing*, 02(04), 373-385. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ars.2013.24040>
- 8) Allbed, A., Kumar, L., & Aldakheel, Y. Y. (2014). Assessing soil salinity using soil salinity and vegetation indices derived from IKONOS high-spatial resolution imageries: Applications in a date palm dominated region. *Geoderma*, 230-231, 1-8.
- 9) Alsharif M. R., H. Rasheed, and A. Khan, "Land use and land cover change detection using remote sensing and GIS techniques in arid regions," *Remote Sensing* 14(5), 1234 (2022).
- 10) Ashraf M., Saeed M. M., and R. H. Qureshi, "Sustainable agriculture and environmental rehabilitation through salinity management in Pakistan," *Irrigation and Drainage Systems* 21(3-4), 211-225 (2007).
- 11) Chandio N. H., Talpur M. A., Tagar A. A., and I. A. Chandio "Soil salinity: A serious environmental issue and plant growth promoting bacteria as one of the tools for its alleviation," *Journal of Engineering, Science & Technology Review* 10(2), 32-35 (2017).
- 12) Chen, H., Zhao, G., Li, Y., Wang, D., & Ma, Y. (2019). Monitoring the seasonal dynamics of soil salinization in the yellow river delta of china using landsat data. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 19(7), 1499-1508. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-19-1499-2019>
- 13) Cui, X., Han, W., Zhang, H., Cui, J., Ma, W., Zhang, L., ... & Li, G. (2022). Estimating soil salinity under sunflower cover in the hetao irrigation district based on unmanned aerial vehicle remote sensing. *Land Degradation & Development*, 34(1), 84-97. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.4445>

- 14) Davis J., Landgrebe D. A., and D. R. Phillips "Remote Sensing: The Quantitative Approach," McGraw-Hill (2019).
- 15) Dwivedi R. S. "Application of principal component analysis to remote sensing," International Journal of Remote Sensing 17(2), 305-312 (1996).
- 16) Dwivedi R. S. "Remote sensing of soils in India," International Journal of Remote Sensing 29(3), 815-832 (2007).
- 17) Dwivedi R. S. "Soil salinity assessment using remote sensing," Natural Resources Forum 25(1), 25-33 (2001).
- 18) Elhag, M. (2016). Detection of land degradation in Egypt using MODIS data. Geocarto International, 31(6), 672-685.
- 19) El-Hamid A. M. A., A. I. Ismail, and S. A. Wahba "Predicting soil salinity using Operational Land Imager 8 (OLI) imagery," International Journal of Remote Sensing 44(3), 789-809 (2023).
- 20) Elnaggar, A. A., & Noller, J. S. (2010). Application of remote-sensing data and decision-tree analysis to mapping salt-affected soils over large areas. Remote Sensing, 2(1), 151-165.
- 21) Farooqi A., S. Khan, and Z. Ahmed "Climate change and its effect on soil salinity in arid and semi-arid regions," Environmental Monitoring and Assessment 195(2), 379 (2023).
- 22) Gautam, G., Kumar, S., & Saha, S. K. (2011). Hyperspectral satellite data in mapping salt-affected soils using linear spectral unmixing analysis. Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing, 40(1), 129-136. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12524-011-0143-x>
- 23) Gojiya, K. M., Rank, H. D., Chauhan, P. M., Patel, D. V., Satasiya, R. M., & Prajapati, G. V. (2023). Remote sensing and gis applications in soil salinity analysis: a comprehensive review. International Journal of Environment and Climate Change, 13(11), 2149-2161. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ijecc/2023/v13i113377>
- 24) Goldshleger, N., Ben-Dor, E., Lugassi, R., & Eshel, G. (2010). Soil degradation monitoring by remote sensing: examples with three degradation processes. Soil Science Society of America Journal, 74(5), 1433-1445. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2009.0351>
- 25) Gorji, T., Yıldırım, A., Sertel, E., & Tanık, A. (2019). Remote sensing approaches and mapping methods for monitoring soil salinity under different climate regimes. International Journal of Environment and Geoinformatics, 6(1), 33-49. <https://doi.org/10.30897/ijegeo.500452>
- 26) Gupta R. and A. Singh, "Assessment of soil salinity using remote sensing and GIS techniques," International Journal of Remote Sensing 43(6), 2321-2338 (2022).
- 27) Hadeed, M. Z., Safdar, M., Ali, A., Shahid, M. A., Tin, T. T., Malik, A., Arif, A., Rashid, R., Raza, A., & Muzammal, H. (2024). Role of Remote Sensing and GIS for Sustainable Crop Production under Climate Change. In J. Mabrouki & M. Azrour (Eds.), *Advancements in Climate and Smart Environment Technology* (pp. 152-172). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-3807-0.ch012>
- 28) He, Q., Li, R., Yang, L., and Zhang, Y. (2023). "Soil salinity monitoring and mapping using multi-temporal remote sensing indices in irrigated arid regions." *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 295, 113649. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2023.113649>.
- 29) Hoa, P. V., Giang, N. V., Binh, N. A., Hai, L. V. H., Pham, T. D., Hasanlou, M., ... & Bui, D. T. (2019). Soil salinity mapping using sar sentinel-1 data and advanced machine learning algorithms: a case study at ben tre province of the mekong river delta (vietnam). Remote Sensing, 11(2), 128. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11020128>

- 30) Huang J., Ma R., and S. Wang, "Mapping soil salinity using Terra ASTER imagery," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 108(1-3), 245-252 (2005).
- 31) Hui, Z. and Liu, Z. (2013). Retrieval of soil salt content base on high resolution remote sensing data. *Proceedings of the 2013 International Conference on Remote Sensing, Environment and Transportation Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/rsete.2013.169>
- 32) Jan M. A., Nawaz M. F., and A. Ali "Assessing the impact of salinity and sodicity on soil fertility and crop yield," *Agricultural Sciences* 14(1), 18-26 (2023).
- 33) Ji, W., Li, S., Hong, Y., et al. (2022). Global Soil Salinity Prediction by Open Soil Vis-NIR Spectral Library. *Remote Sensing*, 14(21), 5627. This study assessed soil salinity at a global scale using Vis-NIR spectroscopy, showing high accuracy in estimating electrical conductivity (EC) across diverse environments using advanced predictive models like XGBoost. [*Remote Sensing*, 2022].
- 34) Jia, X., & Richards, J. A. (1999). Segmented principal components transformation for efficient hyperspectral remote-sensing image display and classification. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 37(1), 538-542.
- 35) Kabiraj S., Debnath B., and A. Roy "Remote sensing for assessing and mapping soil salinity: Techniques and challenges," *Geocarto International* 38(7), 765-784 (2023).
- 36) Kaplan, G., Caner, H., and Cakir, E. (2023). "Comparative analysis of soil salinity indices for precision agriculture." *Agricultural Water Management*, 285, 108205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2023.108205>.
- 37) Khan, N. M., Rastoskuev, V. V., Sato, Y., & Shiozawa, S. (2005). Assessment of hydrosaline land degradation by using a simple approach of remote sensing indicators. *Agricultural Water Management*, 77(1-3), 96-109.
- 38) Kleidman R. G., Luvall J. C., and B. N. Holben "Mapping soil salinity using Landsat ETM+ data in Thailand," *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 26(1), 179-189 (2005).
- 39) Kumar, N. T., Singh, S., Reddy, G. P. O., Mishra, V., & Bajpai, R. (2020). Remote sensing applications in mapping salt affected soils. *Agricultural Reviews*, (Of). <https://doi.org/10.18805/ag.r-2008>
- 40) Kumar, S., Gautam, G., & Saha, S. K. (2014). Hyperspectral remote sensing data derived spectral indices in characterizing salt-affected soils: a case study of indo-gangetic plains of india. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 73(7), 3299-3308. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-014-3613-y>
- 41) Liu, W., Baret, F., Gu, X., Tong, Q., Zheng, L., & Zhang, B. (2003). Evaluation of methods for soil surface moisture estimation from reflectance data. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 24(10), 2069-2083.
- 42) Liu, Y., & Wu, J. (2010). Land transformation and environmental change in China: An overview of the special issue. *Applied Geography*, 30(3), 379-384.
- 43) Liu, Y., Zhang, X., and Feng, X. (2019). "Application of normalized difference salinity index (NDSI) for salt-affected soil analysis in arid regions." *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 83(3), 795-805. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2018.09.0336>.
- 44) Ma, Y., Chen, H., Zhao, G., Wang, Z., & Wang, D. (2020). Spectral index fusion for salinized soil salinity inversion using sentinel-2a and uav images in a coastal area. *IEEE Access*, 8, 159595-159608. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2020.3020325>
- 45) Matinfar H., V. Parsa, and M. Shadmehri "Mapping and monitoring salt-affected soils using remote sensing and GIS techniques," *Geocarto International* 38(6), 723-737 (2023).

- 46) Matsushita B, Yang W, Chen J, Onda Y, Qiu G. Sensitivity of the Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) to Topographic Effects: A Case Study in High-density Cypress Forest. *Sensors*. 2007; 7(11):2636-2651. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s7112636>
- 47) Mehrjardi R. T., Mohammadi J., and H. Khodaverdiloo "Use of Landsat ETM+ data for soil salinity mapping in arid and semi-arid regions," *Iranian Journal of Earth Sciences* 1(2), 149-158 (2008).
- 48) Metternicht, G. I., & Zinck, J. A. (2003). Remote sensing of soil salinity: potentials and constraints. *Remote sensing of environment*, 85(1), 1-20.
- 49) Metternicht, G. I., & Zinck, J. A. (2008). Remote sensing of soil salinization: Impact on land management. CRC Press.
- 50) Mohamed S. M., Ahmed A. A., and S. A. El-Sayed "Evaluation of soil salinity using remote sensing data: Case studies from different regions," *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment* 29, 100674 (2023).
- 51) Mohammed, H. M., & Kumar, L. (2021). Soil Salinity Mapping Using Satellite Data and Machine Learning Approaches in Semi-Arid Regions of India. *Geocarto International*, 36(6), 703-717. This research demonstrated the efficacy of spectral indices and machine learning for identifying salt-affected areas using satellite imagery in semi-arid regions. [Geocarto International, 2021].
- 52) Moisa H. and Gameda D. O., "Application of remote sensing for soil salinity assessment in arid and semi-arid regions," *Journal of Arid Environments* 190, 104522 (2021).
- 53) Narmada M., Sharma P., and A. Kumar, "Soil salinity assessment using spectral indices and field data: A case study from the Punjab region," *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 36(11), 2877-2897 (2015).
- 54) Naz A, Khaliq. A, and S. Ullah "Sustainable agriculture through soil health management in salt-affected regions," *Sustainability* 14(5), 2787 (2022).
- 55) Rahmati O. and N. Hamzehpour, "Principal component analysis of hyperspectral remote sensing data for mineral exploration in the eastern part of Central Iran," *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* 68, 111-119 (2018).
- 56) Rao P. V., Ramesh T., and R. Srinivasan, "Impact of salt-affected soils on crop productivity in India and management strategies," *Agricultural Research* 12(3), 297-305 (2023).
- 57) Rao, B. R. M., Dwivedi, R. S., Venkataratnam, L., & Singh, A. N. (1996). Monitoring salt-affected soils using remote sensing data. *Geocarto International*, 11(4), 41-46.
- 58) Raza A, Shahid MA, Safdar M, Zaman M, Sabir RM, Muzammal H, Ahmed MM. Impact of Land Use and Land Cover Change on Agricultural Production in District Bahawalnagar, Pakistan. *Environmental Sciences Proceedings*. 2024; 29(1):46. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ECRS2023-16644>.
- 59) Raza, A. et al. (2024). Climate Change Impacts on Crop Productivity and Food Security: An Overview. In: Kanga, S., Singh, S.K., Shevkani, K., Pathak, V., Sajan, B. (eds) *Transforming Agricultural Management for a Sustainable Future*. World Sustainability Series. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-63430-7_8
- 60) Richards J. A. "Remote Sensing Digital Image Analysis," Springer-Verlag (1991).
- 61) Sadiq M. A., A. Azad, and A. Hussain, "Soil salinity detection using remote sensing techniques: A review," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 192(10), 677 (2020).

- 62) Safdar, M., Shahid, M. A., Yang, C., Rasul, F., Tahir, M., Raza, A., & Sabir, R. M. (2024). Climate Smart Agriculture and Resilience. In J. Garwi, R. Masengu, & O. Chiwaridzo (Eds.), *Emerging Technologies and Marketing Strategies for Sustainable Agriculture* (pp. 28-52). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-4864-2.ch002>
- 63) Schmid T., Koch M., and J. Gumuzzio "Multispectral remote sensing of soil salinity: Potential and constraints," *Remote Sensing of Environment* 113(1), 70-75 (2008).
- 64) Sharma R. C. And B. K. Mondal, "Soil salinity: Causes, effects, and management," *International Journal of Agricultural Research* 1(1), 61-74 (2006).
- 65) Sharma, L. K., & Singh, S. (2015). Remote sensing techniques for soil salinity assessment: A review. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 1(3), 302-310.
- 66) Srinivasan R., Zhang X., and J. G. Arnold "SWAT model: Current developments and applications," *Hydrological Processes* 36(3), e14382 (2022).
- 67) Taghadosi M. M., Khalili A., and M. Farzamnia "A novel approach for soil salinity classification using Sentinel-2 images," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 191(5), 302 (2019).
- 68) Tuia, D., Ratle, F., Pacifici, F., Kanevski, M. F., & Emery, W. J. (2009). Active learning methods for remote sensing image classification. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 47(7), 2218-2232.
- 69) Verma, K. S., Saxena, R. K., Barthwal, A. K., & Deshmukh, S. N. (1994). Remote sensing technique for mapping salt affected soils. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 15(9), 1901-1914.
- 70) Wang X., Liu H., and Y. Zhang "Global soil salinization and food security: Causes, consequences, and mitigation," *Environmental Research* 216, 114679 (2023).
- 71) Wu, W., & Zhang, G. (2014). Simulating the effects of cropping systems and fertilizer management on soil carbon sequestration in an arid region of Northwest China. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 32(1), 5-14.
- 72) Yang, X., Liu H., Liu, L. and Y. Zhou, "Application of principal component analysis in remote sensing image classification," *Proceedings of the International Conference on Remote Sensing, Environment and Transportation Engineering*, 254-258 (2012).
- 73) Yu L., Yang J., and S. Chen "Monitoring soil salinity using remote sensing technology: A review," *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 31(10), 2489-2501 (2010).
- 74) Zhang, C., Li, W., & Qin, Z. (2011). Estimation of soil salinity using three statistical models based on hyperspectral data in a coastal agricultural area, China. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 32(21), 7399-7414.
- 75) Zhang, R., & Zhu, Q. (2013). Mapping soil salinity with hyperspectral imagery using both regression and classification tree techniques. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 42(3), 859-867.